

Complexes of 3-(*p*-Tolyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-5-ylthiourea with some Bivalent Metal Ions

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In continuation our study of the interaction of thiourea derivatives with the transition metal ions¹, we now report the synthesis of selected metal chelates with the thiourea (I) and also the measurements of the solution stabilities of its bivalent Cu, Ni, Co, Mn and Zn complexes.

Results and Discussion

The acid dissociation constant of the ligand was calculated from the potentiometric titration curve of hydrochloric acid in the presence and absence of the ligand. The formation curve for the proton-ligand system is extended from 0 and 1 in the n_A scale and which indicates that the ligand has one dissociable proton. The log K_1^H value is 9.52. Fig. 1 shows that the n values for all metals are >1.5 . Therefore, ML^+ and ML_2 complexes are formed in solution. The log K_1 and log K_2

Fig. 1. Formation curves for metal chelates of (I) : (1) Co^{II}, (2) Cu^{II}, (3) Ni^{II}, (4) Zn^{II} and (5) Mn^{II}

values for all the complexes were calculated by successive approximation and correction term methods² (Table 1). The log K_1 and log B_2 values follow the order: Mn < Ni < Co < Cu > Zn.

The analytical data show that the ligand forms 1 : 1 complexes with copper(II) and 1 : 2 complexes with cobalt(II) ions. Molar ratio³ and Job's continuous variation⁴ methods were used to confirm the stoichiometry of the complexes.

The low molar conductances (5.0 and 7.0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ for Cu^{II} and Co^{II} complexes, respectively in DMF) reveal the nonionic nature of the complexes and the acetate ion in the Cu^{II} complex is coordinated to the metal ion.

The ir spectrum of the ligand exhibits bands at 3 000, 3 200 (NH) and 1 535 cm^{-1} (C=S). Moreover, the strong ligand band at 1 715 cm^{-1} is tentatively assigned to C=O. The spectra of the complexes show red-shift for both C=S and C=O bonds. In addition, new bands appear in the spectra of the complexes at 1 650 (C=O) and 1 500 cm^{-1} (C-S). This suggests participation of ethoxycarbonyl oxygen and thiocarbonyl sulphur atoms in complex formation.

It is obvious that the ligand might be expected to be uninegatively charged bidentate donor and coordinated to Cu^{II} and Co^{II} via sulphur and oxygen atoms.

Experimental

Analytical grade Cu(CH₃COO)₂·H₂O, NiCl₂·6H₂O, Co(CH₃COO)₂·4H₂O, ZnSO₄·7.2O and MnCl₂·6H₂O were used. All solutions were prepared in deionised H₂O and standardised by routine procedures⁵. 3-(*p*-Tolyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-5-ylthiourea (I) was prepared as previously recommended⁶.

Copper(II) and cobalt(II) complexes were prepared in the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) ratio respectively.

TABLE 1 – FORMATION CONSTANTS OF SOME BIVALENT METAL ION CHELATES FORMED WITH *N*-ETHOXYCARBONYL-*N'*-[1-3-(*p*-TOLYL)-1-PHENYLPYRAZOL-5-YL]THIOUREA (I)

Metal ion	Computational method	Formation constant		
		log K_1	log K_2	log B
H ⁻	Half value	9.52	—	9.52
	Average value	9.55	—	9.55
	Mean	9.53	—	9.53
Cu ²⁺	Half value	6.93	6.3	13.23
	Successive appn	6.699	6.531	13.23
	Correct.on term	6.76	6.47	13.23
	Mean	6.766	6.434	13.20
Ni ²⁺	Half value	4.39	4.16	8.55
	Successive appn	3.947	4.602	8.549
	Correction term	4.11	4.44	8.55
	Mean	4.149	4.331	8.48
Co ²⁺	Half value	6.775	6.66	13.435
	Successive appn	6.474	7.179	13.653
	Corection term	6.455	6.98	13.435
	Mean	6.568	6.94	13.508
Zn ²⁺	Half value	4.245	3.16	7.405
	Successive appn	4.149	3.256	7.405
	Correction term	4.165	3.08	7.245
	Mean	4.186	3.165	7.351
Mn ²⁺	Half value	3.265	3.175	6.440
	Successive appn	2.729	3.71	6.439
	Correction term	2.935	3.505	6.44
	Mean	2.976	3.463	6.939

The metal salt (1 mmol) and the appropriate amount of the ligand, both dissolved in minimum volume of EtOH, were mixed. The pH of the solution was raised to ca 6–7 by addition of dilute NaOH solution. The resulting complexes were washed with 1 : 1 EtOH : H₂O and dried under reduced pressure (estimated at the Microanalysis Unit at Cairo University): (Found : C, 53.0; H, 4.5; N, 10.8; S, 6.0; Cu, 12.9. C₂₂H₂₂N₄O₄SCu

calcd. for : C, 52.6; H, 4.4; N, 11.1; S, 6.4; Cu, 12.6%) and (Found : C, 59.2; H, 5.0; N, 13.2; S, 7.2; Co, 7.0. C₄₀H₃₈N₈O₄S₂Co calcd. for : C, 58.7; H, 4.7; N, 13.7; S, 7.8; Co, 7.2%). All measurements were carried out as reported earlier¹.

Procedure : Mixtures (A-C) were prepared for the determination of the acid dissociation constant of the ligand and formation constants of the metal ion complexes and were titrated potentiometrically : (A) 0.1 M HCl (3.0 ml) + 1.0 M NaCl (5.0 ml); (B) mixture (A) + 0.01 M ligand solutions (10.0 ml); (C) mixture (B) + 0.005 M metal ion solution (4.0 ml). The final volume was made up to 40 ml in each case, so that the solvent composition was 70% EtOH : H₂O and ionic strength 0.1 M. Each mixture was titrated with a carbonate-free 0.15 M NaOH solution in a N₂-atmosphere at 25°. The formation constants of the complexes were determined using the Bjerrum-Calvin method⁷, as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁸. From the pH-titration curves, $\bar{n}_A$, n , pL values were calculated.

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